

**OBTAINING ACTIVATED PHOSPHORUS FERTILIZERS ON THE
BASE OF LOCAL PHOSPHATE WASTE**

B.E. Sultonov,

E.S. Nozimov,

D.S. Kholmatov

Namangan State University 160103,

Republic of Uzbekistan, Namangan, st. Uychi, 316, Uzbekistan.

Abstract. The manuscript provides the results of the process of obtaining activated phosphorus fertilizer (APF) by nitric acid processing of mineralized mass (MM) of phosphate waste, which formed during the sorting stage of thermal beneficiation of Central Kyzylkum (CK) phosphorites.

Key words: mineralized mass, nitric acid, acid concentration, acid norm, activated phosphorus fertilizer.

The main phosphate raw material of our country is Central Kyzylkum (CK) phosphorites with low quality and high carbonate, and from them are produced simple and complex fertilizers with different content of phosphorus. These phosphorites are considered to be very poor in terms of the main component (P_2O_5). Despite the large reserves of this phosphate raw material (PRM), the average amount of P_2O_5 in it is 16.2%. Currently, there are various ways of using these phosphorites: thermal beneficiation, direct acidification and processing with various reagents, etc. Currently, CK phosphorites are thermally enriched at Kyzylkum Phosphorite Combine, and at least 1.800.000 tons of phosphate raw materials are used for this enrichment.

This enrichment method includes the following steps: separation of mined phosphorites into rich fractions, washing of rich phosphorites from chlorine, and high-temperature incineration of the resulting phosphorite raw materials. The main drawbacks of existing technology of enrichment are the following:

1) Formation of phosphate waste called mineralized mass (MM) with a size greater than 5 mm and containing 12-14% P_2O_5 during separation of phosphorites into rich fractions. Its amount is one third of mined phosphate raw materials;

2) During chlorine washing of phosphate raw materials, 15-25% of total P_2O_5 transition to waste in the form of phosphorite powder (sludge). This phosphorite sludge (PS) was also not reused in any way. In total, 42% of the P_2O_5 in the phosphate raw material goes to the mineralized mass and phosphorite sludge waste;

3) The high value of the calcium module (2.0–2.1) in washed and burned concentrate (WBPC), as removal of the CaO free formed at decomposing of lime carbonate is not provided [1-3].

This thesis material presents the results of obtaining activated phosphorus fertilizers based on MM and nitric acid. The following MM sample was taken for laboratory research: 14.60% P_2O_{5t} ; 3.07% $P_2O_{5ac.c.a.}$; 43.99% CaO; 1.01% MgO; 14.11% CO_2 ; 1.04% Al_2O_3 ; 0.89% Fe_2O_3 ; 1.58% SO_3 ; 1.30% F; 1.02% H_2O ; CaO: P_2O_5 – 3.01 and 10.82% insoluble residue. MM this chemical composition was decomposed with nitric acid at concentrations 30.0; 35.0; 40.0; 45.0; 50.0; 55.0 and 58.78% and it at a norm of 100% relative to the formation of dicalcium phosphate.

The laboratory tests results are shown in Table 1. It is seen that the

Table 1

Chemical composition of activated phosphorus fertilizers (norm of HNO_3 - 100%)

No of experiments	Chemical composition, %							
	P_2O_{5t}	$P_2O_{5ac.c.a.}$	$P_2O_{5sw.}$ s.	CaO _t	CaO _{ac.c.a.}	CaO _{w.} s.	N	Degree of transition of P_2O_5 to liquid phase, %
Concentration of HNO_3 – 30.0%								
1	17.23	7.41	2.41	39.11	19.15	2.80	1.02	24.06
Concentration of HNO_3 – 35.0%								
2	17.27	7.51	2.45	39.12	19.35	2.89	1.04	24.44
Concentration of HNO_3 – 40.0%								
3	17.32	7.62	2.48	39.14	19.56	2.92	1.08	24.86

Concentration of HNO₃ – 45.0%								
4	17.38	7.73	2.50	39.22	19.99	2.99	1.11	25.20
Concentration of HNO₃ – 50.0%								
5	17.44	7.84	2.55	39.27	20.15	3.09	1.13	25.35
Concentration of HNO₃ – 55.0%								
6	17.48	7.96	2.58	39.33	20.40	3.18	1.18	25.57
Concentration of HNO₃ – 58.78%								
7	17.59	8.17	2.61	39.52	20.94	3.22	1.20	25.76

concentration of nitric acid does not significantly affect the quantitative indicator of P₂O_{5t}, which is the main nutrient component in the activated phosphorus fertilizer samples. For example, nitric acid was taken at a concentration of 30% the amount of total P₂O_{5t} in the fertilizer sample is equal to 17.23%, and when 58.78% nitric acid is used, it is equal to 17.59%, that is, it increases by only 0.36%. The acceptable forms of P₂O₅ and CaO increase from 7.41 to 8.17% (by 0.76%) and from 19.15 to 20.94% (by 1.79%), respectively. It can be seen that it slightly effects the concentration of nitric acid. All the obtained samples of activated phosphorus-activated fertilizers have relative acceptable values of P₂O₅ and CaO from 43.00 to 46.44% and from 48.96 to 52.98%, respectively, and fertilizers with such quantitative indicators do not answer the requirements by agriculture. Another drawback of these obtained results is that 24.06 to 25.76% of the total P₂O₅ in the phosphate feedstock passes into the liquid phase, i.e. as waste.

In the new works we will study about increasing the phosphorus content in the obtained fertilizers and reducing the transfer of phosphorus into the liquid phase.

References

1. Sultonov B.E., Namazov Sh.S., Zakirov B.S. Chemical enrichment of low-grade phosphorites of Central Kyzyl kum // Journal of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, Sofia, 49, 3, 2014, 288-292.
2. Sultonov B.E., Namazov Sh.S., Zakirov B.S. Investigation of nitric acid beneficiation of low grade phosphorites from Central Kyzylkum Journal of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, Sofia, 50, 1, 2015, 26-34.

3.Sultonov B.E., Namazov S.Sh., Zakirov B.S. Some aspects of nitric acid beneficiation of Central Kyzylkum’s phosphorites The Development of Science in the 21st Century: Natural and Technical Sciences. The Collection of Scientific Papers. Part 2. Research in General & Inorganic Chemistry, pp. 126-129. Ron Bee & Associates New York 10.05. 2015